

Two newly isolated phages infecting *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*

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Abstract

Vibrio is a bacterial genus that can be widely found in estuarine, coastal, and open-ocean waters around the globe. *Vibrio alginolyticus* and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* specifically are known for being pathogenic, causing infections (known as 'vibriosis') in marine organisms and humans. Development of effective methods for treating *Vibrio* is essential. Considering the rapid development of antibiotic resistance, phage therapy emerges as a potentially more sustainable and effective solution, prompting continued efforts to isolate new phages that target pathogenic *Vibrio* species. For this research, water samples were collected from three aquaculture locations, different phages (designated as phiST and phiLG) that target *V. parahaemolyticus* were successfully isolated from two samples. Double-layer agar plates were employed to culture the samples, which were then purified three times. The phiST plaques were more distinctly visible and slightly smaller in diameter (0.9 - 1.0 mm as opposed to 1.2 mm for the phiLG plaques). Further analysis of these phages through transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was completed. The phiST are podoviruses with a head diameter of 67.90 ± 2.03 nm (average \pm SD), while phiLG are myoviruses with head diameters and tail lengths of 84.43 ± 3.78 nm and 118.69 ± 2.36 nm, respectively. DNA genome sequencing tests are currently being done for further analysis, after tests of quality and quantity of the phage DNA samples was confirmed. This research will be extended by further analyzing and characterizing these two newly isolated phages, and eventually developing their potential in therapeutic purposes.

1. Introduction

Vibrio is a genus of bacteria, that inhabits estuarine, coastal, and open-ocean waters around the globe [1]. *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus* specifically are two *Vibrio* species that are known for being pathogenic, causing vibriosis in marine animals and severe intestinal and extraintestinal illnesses in humans if infected [2]. Humans risk contracting *Vibrio* infections when they consume raw or undercooked shellfish, especially oysters [3]. Overall,

there is an estimated annual cost of \$30 million from the health damages that *V. vulnificus*, *V. parahaemolyticus* and *V. alginolyticus* induce in the United States [4]. Thus, *Vibrio* poses an enormous threat to the aquaculture industry, not only for human consumption but also food preservation and transportation.

For individuals, current methods for preventing *Vibrio* infections include wearing gloves and washing hands thoroughly when handling raw shellfish, always cooking shellfish fully before consumption, and vaccination [5]. Also, eating seafood within two hours of removing it from the refrigerator can reduce risk of infection [6]. As for regulatory protocol, techniques such as processing shellfish using disinfected seawater and storing seafood at no more than 10 °C have been implemented to reduce *Vibrio* growth [6]. Measuring *V. parahaemolyticus* levels in seafood has also become common procedure as well, with acceptable levels being ≤ 100 most probable number/gram for raw seafood consumption, and non-detectable levels/25 grams for cooked seafood [6].

In order to treat these *Vibrio* infections, one valid option is phage therapy. Phage therapy relies on virulent phages to initiate lytic cycles in host bacteria, which ultimately kills the bacteria and acts as an effective way to control infections. Specifically, phage cocktails, or a mixture of phages with different lytic capabilities, have been shown to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the treatment in killing pathogenic bacteria [7]. In addition, phage therapy holds many benefits over other methods of killing bacteria such as antibiotics. As for antibiotics, they can be extremely efficient at exterminating a wider range of bacteria at first, but with time, overuse of antibiotics will lead to antibiotic resistance, and thus antibiotics will become less effective. On the other hand, though the specificity of phages makes them less widely compatible, phage therapy is lower in toxicity and produces less side effects [8].

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Moreover, phage therapy remains just as effective, even on antibiotic resistant bacteria, deeming them an essential method to combat the dangers of antibiotic resistance. Furthermore, combining phage therapy such as phage cocktails with antibiotics can especially increase the effectiveness of the treatment, through the method of phage-antibiotic synergy, which has been shown to aid the phages in increasing their activity against their host bacteria [9].

Thus, the research conducted in this paper aims to expand the current collection of phages against vibriosis by isolating and characterizing new phages to treat harmful *Vibrio* spp. infections. These efforts will be useful in providing novel insight and direction in the development of phage therapy for *Vibrio* infection control in the aquaculture industry.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Bacteria Inoculation and Phylogenetic Analysis

First, the host bacteria used in the experiments were inoculated, specifically being two strains of the *Vibrio* species, *V. alginolyticus* ATCC 17749 and *V. parahaemolyticus* 1.1997. The bacterial colonies were obtained from pure cultures, that were previously prepared and stored in Rich Organic (RO) agar plates [10], using sterile inoculation loops. The bacteria was then inoculated into 50- mL tubes filled with 20 mL of liquid RO culture media. To allow the bacteria to grow to the exponential growth phase, these tubes were placed in a shaker set to 37 °C for 4 hours, at a speed of 180 rpm.

A phylogenetic tree of several related species from the *Vibrio* genus was also created using the MEGA11 software [11]. This tree was constructed using bacterial 16S rRNA gene sequences with the neighbor-joining method and 1,000 bootstrap replicates. The 16S rRNA gene sequences were obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database, and their serial numbers are denoted in the phylogenetic tree along with the species names.

2.2. Phage sample preparation

The phage samples were extracted from sea water that was collected from three separate locations in Guangdong Province, China, specifically the Shatou seafood market (22.78 N, 113.76 E), Longgang Pengrong market (22.66 N, 114.06 E), and Zhongshan mariculture farm (22.48 N, 113.21 E). The original samples were 100 mL of sea water, and to obtain the existing phages from this water, a 0.22- μ m filter was used to filter the water samples, which left us with only the potential phage stock, filtering out all other unwanted organisms and debris. To increase the concentration of any desired phages infecting the two *Vibrio* strains, the filtered phage solution was mixed with the inoculated *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus* bacteria culture prepared in the previous step, in a 1:20 ratio (1 mL of phage

stock to 20 mL of inoculated bacteria solution). The test tubes were incubated in the shaker for 24 hours, again at 37 °C and 180 rpm. After incubation, the solution was run through the 0.22- μ m filters once again to extract the phage virions from the phage-bacterium mixture.

2.3. Dilute phage samples

Serial dilution was employed to dilute and prepare the phage samples for culturing. The multiple different concentrations of dilution were to increase the likelihood of obtaining a plate with singular, isolated phage plaques to allow for easier extraction. To do this, the phage stock was diluted in the two different *Vibrio* bacterial solutions with five different levels of dilution: 10-2, 10-4, 10-6, 10-8, 10-10, each in a 15-mL test tube. After all the tubes were filled with the proper amount of diluted phage solution, all five tubes were allowed to incubate in a dark area (e.g., a cabinet) for 30 minutes. This step is to allow ample time for the phages to inject their genetic material into the host cells.

2.4. Double-Layer agar plates

The double-layer agar plate method [12] was used to culture the phages, with the end goal of extracting phage plaques for further purification. The purpose of this double-layer agar plate method is to ensure that all phage plaques occur on the same, thin layer of culture medium, which allows us to pick up single plaques without the possibility of the formation of overlapping, impure plaques.

The diluted phage samples (for each strain: five from Shatou, five from Longgang, and five from Zhongshan) were prepared, as well as petri dishes that were already filled with 20 mL of pre-solidified RO agar (1.5%). Then, a flask of solidified 0.5% soft agar RO culture medium was heated until fully liquified. 6 mL of the liquified agar was poured into each of the tubes of diluted phage samples, and the resulting mixture was poured into the pre-solidified agar petri dishes. The newly poured agar layers were allowed to cool down and solidify again before the petri dishes were sealed and stored in a 37 °C incubator for 24 hours to wait for phage plaque growth.

For the first cycle of phage culturing on the double-layer agar plates, only plates of *V. parahaemolyticus*-1.1997 mixed with the phage solution of Shatou and Longgang seawater samples exhibited phage plaque growth, so the following steps of the experimentation were only performed on these two phage plaques.

2.5. Phage purification

To further purify the phage plaques that grew on the double-layer agar plates, singular plaques were removed and cultured on new agar plates. To do this, individual plaques were cut out using 1-mL micropipette tips, and stored in 1 mL of storage medium (SM) buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, 0.1 M NaCl, and 8 mM MgSO₄ (pH 7.59)). The

plaque-buffer tubes were thoroughly vibrated using the vortex oscillator, with the goal of releasing as many phage virions as possible from the solid plaque into the liquid buffer. After the samples of the singular phage plaques formed on the bacterial lawns of *V. parahaemolyticus*-1.1997, three cycles of phage purification were completed for each unique sample. To do this, the 1 mL of SM buffer-phage plaque solution was used, and the processes of serial dilution, pouring double-layer agar plates, and incubation were repeated three times each, which resulted in two final, pure phage plaque samples (designated as phiST (Shatou) and phiLG (Longgang)) that were utilized for further sequencing.

2.6. Expanding cultivation and ultracentrifugation

Once both phage samples were purified, their cultivation was expanded from 1 mL phage plaque solutions into a 200 mL bacterial culture, and finally an 800 mL bacterial culture from which the phage sediment could be extracted. Then, the 1 L phage lysates were centrifuged at $10,000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 minutes, after which they were filtered once more using $0.22\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ filters. Then, PEG8000 was added to the solution, after which it was kept at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours to precipitate the phages. The solution was then centrifuged once more at $10,000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 minutes, from which the sediment was extracted. This sediment solution, kept in 6 mL of SM buffer, was put through cesium chloride density gradient centrifugation (1.3, 1.5, and 1.7 g/mL layers) for 24 hours to achieve the visible phage band, which was desalinized using SM buffer.

2.7. Transmission electron microscopy

The phages were then morphologically analyzed through TEM. $20\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of desalinized phage solution was dropped onto carbon-coated copper grids, which were stored in a dark area for 30 min to allow absorption of the solution. In order to view the phages, the sample was negatively stained using 1% phosphotungstic acid for 1 min, and then allowed to air dry for 10 min, after which TEM phage images were taken, and phage size was measured. The device used was a Hitachi TEM system, set to 80 kV, and particle size was measured from at least 5 particles using ImageJ software (Schneider et al., 2012).

2.8. DNA extraction

To extract the phage DNA, 1 mL of purified phage solution was drawn, into which $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of protease K, $20\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), and $10\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ EDTA solution were added. This mixture was fully mixed and incorporated using a vortex oscillator, then kept in a $55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ water bath for 3 hours to preserve constant temperature. Then, the sample was further purified. This was done by mixing an equal volume of phenol: chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) into the digested phage sample, and centrifuging the mixture at $12,000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min. Once the upper aqueous

phase was extracted from the centrifuged sample, this process was repeated twice to ensure further purification. Upon completion of the last repetition, the upper aqueous phase was transferred into a new centrifuge tube. This resulting solution was then treated with an equal volume of isopropanol, which was fully incorporated and allowed to settle overnight at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The following day, the sample was centrifuged once again at $12,000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min, from which the supernatant was discarded, and the remaining nucleic acid precipitate was rinsed with pre-cooled $500\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of 70% ethanol solution. The resulting sample was centrifuged a final time at $12,000\times g$ and $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min, and the nucleic acid precipitate was kept to air dry in a fume hood. The DNA was then resuspended in TE buffer and sent to test for DNA concentration and subsequent sequencing analysis.

2.9. DNA sequencing

The concentrations of the phage DNA samples were tested to determine whether they were concentrated enough to administer further testing such as DNA sequencing. This was tested using a Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer machine. The total volume and amount of each sample were also tested and recorded. Following concentration and mass tests, the phage DNA samples were run through a gel electrophoresis test to ensure the samples retained their integrity and viability for further sequencing. The electrophoresis test utilized 1.2% agarose gel, at 80V constant voltage for 40 minutes, and the comparison was a phage DNA marker. The phiST and phiLG phage DNA is now being sequenced using the Illumina HiSeq 4000 platform with a 300-bp paired-end DNA library.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Host bacteria

The phage bacteria host were *V. alginolyticus* ATCC 17749^(T) and *V. parahaemolyticus*-1.1997^(T) (also known as ATCC 17802^(T)). Through phylogenetic analysis, both species were determined to be closely related to *V. harveyi*, and they are all common pathogenic bacterial species (Figure. 1a). When cultured on RO agar plates, *V. parahaemolyticus* exhibited more opaque white circular colonies, each with a more solid dot in the middle and a milkier surrounding (Figure. 1b). *V. alginolyticus*' colonies were smaller than those of *V. parahaemolyticus*, and also slightly more translucent, but still milky white in color (Figure. 1c). After incubating the inoculated bacteria liquid at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 180 rpm in a shaker for four hours, the culture media-bacteria liquid became turbid and milkier in color, compared to its original translucent pale yellow, as the bacteria experienced their logarithmic growth phase (Figure. 1d).

The reason these strains of *Vibrio* were chosen as targets is

Figure 1. Details on the *Vibrio* host bacteria used. **a.** a phylogeny of type strains of species of the *Vibrio* genus, constructed using bacterial 16S rRNA gene sequences with neighbor-joining method and 1,000 bootstrap replicates. Highlighted in red are the two bacterial species that were investigated, *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus*. **b.** and **c.** photographs of the pure bacterial colonies of *V. parahaemolyticus* **b** and *V. alginolyticus* **c** from which all of the samples throughout the experimentation process were extracted. **d.** inoculated bacteria in shaker incubator.

due to the damage that these bacteria cause to the aquaculture industry, as well as food preservation and transportation. *Vibrio* bacteria can be found in estuarine, coastal and open-ocean waters throughout the world [13], and certain strains including *V. alginolyticus* and *V. parahaemolyticus* are infectious to humans [13]. In fact, *V. parahaemolyticus* is the most commonly reported species in *Vibrio* infections, and it is also the species that I was able to isolate phages for. These bacteria often inhabit popular seafood, including fish, shrimp, shellfish, and oysters. Consumption of raw and uncooked contaminated seafood is a primary cause of human *Vibrio* spp. infections, and symptoms of *V. parahaemolyticus* infections include nausea, vomiting, headaches, chills, and diarrhea, and more severe infections can even end in death [13]. On the other hand, *V. alginolyticus* infections are relatively rarer, but they are known to cause serious soft tissue infections, sepsis, and other extraintestinal infections [14]. Furthermore, *Vibrio* bacteria cannot be exterminated by freezing [15], meaning that *Vibrio* can be spread through refrigerated transportation of its seafood carriers.

Evidently, *Vibrio* bacterial infections pose a serious threat to the seafood and other mariculture markets, and finding an effective treatment to kill these bacteria is essential. Therefore, I decided to try and further develop a method of fighting *Vibrio* infestation in seafood, through phage therapy. By isolating phages that specifically target *V. parahaemolyticus*, these phages can potentially be used to treat seafood/marine organisms before consumption or transport to kill the harmful bacteria.

3.2. Water samples

Water sampling locations from aquaculture markets with known carrier organisms of *Vibrio* bacteria were intentionally chosen, and also specific areas/tanks that had relatively turbid sea water, to increase the likelihood of finding applicable phages in the samples. In addition, samples were collected from three separate locations to increase the diversity of phage sources. Specifically, 100 μ L water samples were collected from three separate sources: sewer water from Shatou seafood market (22.78 N, 113.76 E), sea water from Longgang Pengrong market (22.66 N, 114.06 E), and sea water from Zhongshan mariculture farm (22.48 N, 113.21 E) (Table. 1). Of these three samples, only the Shatou and Longgang ones successfully yielded phages that targeted *V. parahaemolyticus*, and none of the samples yielded any phage plaques that targeted *V. alginolyticus*.

3.3. Phage plaques

Phage plaques were successfully identified on the double-layer agar plates from the Shatou and Longgang water samples that target *V. parahaemolyticus*. These plaques were visible 24 hours after incubation of the plates in the 37 $^{\circ}$ C incubator. The plaques on the phiST plates were

Figure 2. The phage plaque results. **a.** is a plate photograph of the phiST 10^{-6} dilution level plate, and **b.** is a plate photograph of the phiLG 10^{-2} dilution level plate. The arrows in both images designate some phage plaques. There is a 5 mm reference scale in the bottom left corner of the images.

consistently more clearly visible than those on the phiLG plates; the phiST plaques were circular and had a diameter of 0.9 - 1.0 mm each, with a distinct edge and highly transparent interior that made them easier to observe when held up to a light source (Figure. 2a). On the other hand,

Table 1. Detailed information of three water samples that were obtained for isolation of phages against pathogenic *Vibrio* species. The last two columns represent whether or not phages that target each *Vibrio* species from the water samples were successfully isolated (+: infected; -: uninfected).

Location	Coordinates	Date of Collection (MM/DD/YYYY)	Water Source	<i>V. parahaemolyticus</i>	<i>V. alginolyticus</i>
Shatou seafood market	22.78 N, 113.76 E	04/16/2023	Sewage water	+	-
Longgang Pengrong market	22.66 N, 114.06 E	06/25/2023	Sea water, from seafood organism habitats	+	-
Zhongshan mariculture farm	22.48 N, 113.21 E	06/22/2023	Sea water, from seafood organism habitats	-	-

the phiLG plaques were much cloudier and difficult to spot. They were also circular in shape, with a diameter of around 1.2 mm each, with cloudier edges and an opaquer interior that resulted in a faded appearance, blurred with the rest of the agar (Figure. 2b). Also, the phiST phage plaques were more densely concentrated, appearing at all the dilution levels (10^{-2} through 10^{-10}), while the phiLG phage plaques tended to only appear at the less diluted levels (10^{-2} through 10^{-4}).

These phage plaque characteristics remained strongly consistent for all of the rounds of purification, indicating a successful purification process and consistent target phages. Additionally, the stark differences between the plaques from the two water samples suggests that the two phage isolates are different, and that they have different efficiency in terms of lytic cycles. Moreover, considering the transparency and visibility of the plaques, I infer that phage phiST may be more effective at killing *V. parahaemolyticus*, due to the more distinctly visible plaques, which can potentially indicate that the bacteria within each plaque have been removed more thoroughly than phiLG. However, further research into the correlation between phage productivity and plaque morphology would be necessary to make definitive conclusions [16].

3.4. Phage bands and morphology

Utilizing the process of cesium chloride (CsCl) density-gradient ultracentrifugation, the phages were separated from bacterial debris in the samples [17]. This CsCl gradient ultracentrifugation is based on the sedimentation principle, as the denser phages settle down quicker than the bacterial debris when under a strong centrifugal force. As depicted in Figures 3a. and 3b., visible phage bands were obtained for both phiST and phiLG. However, the phiST band was noticeably more vibrant in color and visibly thicker than the fainter phiLG phage band, indicating a higher number of phiST phages than phiLG phages present in the samples. The phiST phage band was also notably lower in the test tube compared to the phiLG band, indicating that phiST phages are denser in composition than phiLG phages. Upon analysis of the TEM photographs depicted in Figures 3c. and 3d., the phiST phage appears to be a podovirus, with a hexagonal head that has an average diameter of 67.90 ± 2.03 nm, and a tail that is not portrayed clearly enough in the TEM images to measure. On the other hand, the phiLG

Figure 3. The visible phage bands following ultracentrifugation and corresponding TEM images of phage particles. a. and b. are the visible phage bands of phiST and phiLG, respectively. The blue arrows indicate the phage band, while the white arrows indicate the bacterial debris. c. and d. are the TEM images of phiST and phiLG, respectively. In the bottom right corner of the TEM images, there is a 200 nm reference scale. Before TEM imaging, the phiST sample was diluted 10 \times to ensure clearer viewing.

phages are myoviruses, and they have larger heads at an average diameter of 84.43 ± 3.78 nm, that also appear hexagonal in shape. Furthermore, the tails of the phiLG phages have an average length of 118.69 ± 2.36 nm.

Podoviruses and myoviruses both belong to a class of tailed phages called *Caudovirales*. As a podovirus, phiST has a very short tail that is almost indistinguishable in the TEM imaging. On the other hand, phiLG is classified as a myovirus due to its long contractile tail, distinguishing it from the family of *Siphoviridae* (phages with long, non-contractile tails) [18]. Thus, the morphological analysis of the two phages confirmed that they are two distinct phage isolates, which is consistent with the morphological differences observed in the phage plaques.

Figure 4. Results from testing of the phiST and phiLG phage DNA samples. **a.** is a table outlining information on the concentration, volume, and total amount of each of the phage DNA samples (phiST and phiLG). **b.** is the image of gel electrophoresis results of phiST (second column, serial number 1) and phiLG (third column, serial number 2) DNA samples, compared to phage DNA marker (first column).

3.5. DNA sequencing

To further analyze the properties of these phages, DNA testing on the purified nucleic acid precipitates was begun. The concentrations, amounts, and gel electrophoresis performance were tested to determine whether the samples qualify for full genome sequencing.

Preliminary testing on the concentration, volume, and total mass/amount of each of the phage samples was conducted (Figure. 4a). Based on these measurements, the samples qualified for further testing in terms of genome sequencing and analysis, which will be carried out in the coming month. The results showed that the phiST sample was much higher in concentration (934 ng/ μ L) and amount (23.35 μ g) than the phiLG sample (55 ng/ μ L and 1.37 μ g).

A gel electrophoresis test was also ran on phiST and phiLG (Figure. 4b). The comparison marker, illustrated by column one in (Figure. 4), is a λ phage DNA marker, whose length is known to be 48,502 base pairs [19]. Based on a visual comparison of the three electrophoresis samples, phiST's DNA genome appears to be rather similar in size to the marker, while the phiLG DNA genome appears to be slightly smaller than that of the marker, as its electrophoresis DNA band is farther down on the agarose gel. This prediction is based on the knowledge that shorter DNA fragments have higher mobility than longer fragments during gel electrophoresis tests, and thus shorter fragments travel farther under the same time constraints.

The information on phage concentrations, amounts, and gel electrophoresis imaging are only preliminary results obtained to confirm validity of the samples so that they may be further analyzed. Thus, testing for full DNA genome sequencing of both phages is now underway following qualification of both phiST and phiLG samples, but is currently incomplete. These DNA sequencing results will become a subject of future analysis and understanding of the phages

as discussed below.

3.6. Future implications

First and foremost, in terms of future extension of these experiments, analyzing and characterizing the purified phage plaques is a viable option. Specifically, determining the phages' host ranges (i.e., lysis profiles) is an important focus. Additionally, completion of DNA sequencing to identify the phages' gene profiles would be extremely important to expanding knowledge of the phage - bacterium interactions, by opening up access to any previous research that may have been conducted on these phages. This helps build knowledge on the potential applications of these phage isolates.

Another aspect of these experiments that can be further developed is magnified photography techniques for the phage plaques; as shown in Figure 2b, I was unable to capture clear photographs of the phage plaques, especially for phiLG. These plaques were already very blurred and cloudy to the human eye when they were observed in the laboratory, so future investigation into optimal photography methods for these phage plaques could provide more detailed insight into the plaque morphology of these phages. Another way to potentially improve visibility of the phage plaques is to decrease the agar concentration of the top layer when pouring the double layer agar culture plates, so that the formation of phage plaques may become larger (Serwer & Wright, 2020). Additionally, Thiosulfate Citrate Bile Salts Sucrose (TCBS) agar (Pfeffer & Oliver, 2003) could be utilized in any further testing, to darken the appearance of the bacterial lawn, and increase the contrast between phage plaques and the bacterial lawn.

Further testing on these isolated phages is essential because it can be applied to expand and develop phage therapies for treating *V. parahaemolyticus* infections. These infections cause great damages to the mariculture industry due to their

negative impact on human health as well as complicating the processes of food preservation and transportation. Furthermore, *Vibrio* bacteria have developed various significant antibiotic resistances due to misuse of antibiotics in treating aquaculture organisms [20], which in turn emphasizes the importance of phage therapy as a more effective approach to treating *Vibrio* infections in marine organisms. Additionally, *V. parahaemolyticus* is the most prevalent species of the family in terms of causing infection, so the implications of successful phage therapies for this bacterial species would be vastly relevant to improving the aquaculture industry. As two different phages that each have the potential to be developed into more refined methods for terminating *Vibrio* spp. infections have already been isolated through the processes in this paper, I hope that further exploration of this research will lead to important developments in human health and aquaculture.

4. Conclusion

This experiment successfully yielded phages targeting *V. parahaemolyticus* from both the Shatou and Longgang water samples. Through purification and expanding cultivation of the phages, TEM and DNA tests were successfully employed, which confirmed that the phiST and phiLG are unique. The isolation of these two new phages represents a significant contribution to the scientific community, increasing the diversity of phages available for phage therapy in the fight against *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* infections. Though the experiments in DNA sequencing are not yet complete, this has become a primary focus of my current research. In the future, I intend to continue efforts to isolate more phages targeting *Vibrio* bacterial strains, to develop the potential of phage therapy in effective treatment of vibriosis.

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